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LIST OF ACRONYMS

API	Application Programming Interface
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
CEMS	Copernicus Earth Monitoring Service
CLC	Corine Land Cover
CLMS	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service
CURE	Copernicus for Urban Resilience in Europe
DIAS	Data and Information Access Services
EC	European Commission
EIONET	European Environment Information and Observation Network
EMS	Emergency Management Service
EO	Earth Observation
ESA	European Space Agency
FUA	Functional Urban Area

GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
HRL	High Resolution Layer
OSM	Open Street Maps
SIS	Sectoral Information System
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
UA	Urban Atlas
UHI	Urban Heat Island

1 INTRODUCTION

This document is the first deliverable of WP6 of the CURE (Copernicus for Urban Resilience in Europe) Project, Deliverable D6.1 entitled ‘Scenarios for CURE integration to Copernicus’.

The goal of WP6 is to assess the CURE system for its credibility to deliver on innovation, enhancement of the state of the art and real impact for the stakeholders considered, e.g. earth observation (EO) scientists, city service providers, city users and ultimately the citizens. WP6 aims to develop plausible scenarios about how the CURE system eventually could be integrated into the existing service architecture of Copernicus, perform a benchmarking exercise to show the added value of the CURE applications and perform an economic feasibility analysis.

Before initiating this work could, there were several aspects about the different CURE applications that needed to be clarified in detail. Therefore, we asked all application developers to fill out a detailed questionnaire on the aspects of their applications that are related to the WP6 topics. The following questions were asked:

- Question 1: Describe your service-to-be in technical detail (include schemes if possible), while addressing these sub-questions:
 - What data does your service need?
 - Does your code run with raw input data or does it require preprocessed data?
 - How much storage does your interim and output data need?
 - Does your service contain more than one task (series of script executions)?
 - What resources does your service need for processing one unit (Cores, RAM)?
 - Do you use Docker?
- Question 2: Will your service be user-interactive (how?) or do you only provide output data/maps?
- Question 3: How do you see your service evolve on the long term (after the CURE project)?
- Question 4: What is the added value for scientists/urban stakeholders over existing services? Please address in your answer these sub-questions:
 - Is there any commercial service available in the market that provides a similar solution? (i.e. which are the main "competitor services" offering alternative solutions to yours)?
 - What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to your service?
 - Do you know any new service in progress of development (with TRL 7 or 8) that could compete in the future with your service?
- Question 5: How easily can your service be upscaled to other cities (both in Europe and outside Europe)?
- Question 6: Is your service linked with existing Copernicus services?

All returned questionnaires are available in Appendix A.

In this Deliverable, we focus on the aspects of the services that are relevant to a potential uptake of the CURE system in the Copernicus architecture. In Chapter 2, we focus on the structure of Copernicus, and which elements define a typical Copernicus service. In Chapter 3, we assess the current status of the CURE applications in light of the elements required for uptake as a Copernicus service. Finally, in Chapter 4, we present a pathway towards a mature CURE service portfolio that would fit perfectly in the Copernicus program, through 3 scenarios.

2 COPERNICUS OVERSIGHT

2.1 Copernicus structure

The Copernicus programme (www.copernicus.eu/) is a joint space contribution of the European Commission (EC) and the European Space Agency (ESA) to the Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS), serving the needs of Europe's policy makers and embracing the important role of user uptake. Data and services derived from EO systems potentially combined with satellite navigation and satellite-based telecommunication, contribute to several public policies and economic sectors such as environmental protection, transport safety, precision farming, control of fishery stocks, detection of oil spills, as well as urban and regional planning (Riedler et al. 2020). New fields of applications are constantly emerging including tourism, cultural heritage, smart cities, or humanitarian assistance. Copernicus has a strong focus on the user uptake component, justifying the huge pre-investments to ensure free data availability.

Currently, the Copernicus data and services are structured in 6 thematic areas (Figure 1). Urban-focussed data and services are spread over the different thematic areas. Climate-related indicators for urban areas (e.g. Urban Heat Island maps) can be found in the Climate Change service, urban land use information (e.g. Urban Atlas) can be found in the Land service and urban risk mapping (e.g. flood maps) can be found in the Emergency service.

Figure 1. Current Copernicus service structure.

However, a new vision of the Copernicus structure is currently emerging, in which both physical regional Copernicus hubs and virtual Copernicus hubs would be established (Riedler et al. 2020). The objectives of these so called Copernicus knowledge and innovation hubs are to boost the user uptake and the development of information services, facilitate an effective transfer of knowledge, encourage cooperation, explore synergies and increase targeted capacity building and training.

Their core activities would focus on (EARSC 2020):

Invent – visualizing research outcome and the distributed expertise, both in thematic and methodological aspects

Inform – reaching out to administrations and the public at large

Innovate –bridging the gap between academia and industry through monitoring innovation and uptake

Interact – bringing Copernicus Academy members together with stakeholders and users

The knowledge hubs will be structured in more thematic areas than the current Copernicus services (Figure 2), and there is a specific application area focussed on urban areas (Sustainable urban development). The CURE system would certainly fit in this area.

Figure 2. Application areas of the Copernicus Knowledge Hubs (EARSC 2020).

2.2 Typical Copernicus service

In order to develop the CURE applications in a way that enables uptake as a Copernicus service, it is important to have a good understanding of how a typical Copernicus service looks like.

While there are several services that focus on urban areas, we highlight here a service that was developed by VITO in the framework of the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Sectoral Information System (SIS) European Health contract, as it is strongly linked to the CURE services. In this service, a high resolution (100m) dataset of climate variables (air temperature, humidity and wind speed) was established through simulations with VITO's UrbClim model (De Ridder et al. 2015), for 100 cities in Europe (Figure 3). The model was set up with Copernicus data sources (e.g. land use and vegetation cover maps, large-scale meteorology) and generated data for a time period of 10 years. Most importantly, a large and differentiated stakeholder community was gathered, that confirmed the added value of this dataset, and applied it in their field of research. This was a crucial step to convince the Copernicus program to invest in the service.

The screenshot shows the Copernicus Climate Change Service website. At the top, there are logos for the European Union, Copernicus, ECMWF, and the Climate Change Service. Below the logos is a navigation bar with links: Home, Search, Datasets, Applications, Toolbox, FAQ, and Live. The main heading is "Climate variables for cities in Europe from 2008 to 2017". Underneath, there are three tabs: "Overview" (selected), "Download data", and "Documentation". The "Overview" tab contains the following text:

The dataset contains air temperature, specific humidity, relative humidity and wind speed for 100 European cities for the current climate.

The data were generated using the urban climate model UrbClim, developed at VITO. This model was designed to simulate and study the urban heat island effect (UHI) and other urban climate variables at a spatial resolution of 100 metres. The unique capabilities of UrbClim allow to generate spatially explicit timeseries of hourly variables from which a variety of indicators can be retrieved in postprocessing at the scale of a city neighbourhood.

For this specific dataset, the ERA5 reanalysis large-scale weather conditions are downscaled to agglomeration-scale. UrbClim then computes the impact of urban development on the most frequent weather parameters, such as temperature and humidity.

The 100 European cities for the urban simulations were selected based on user requirements within the health community. Furthermore, a high spatial distribution was aimed with specific focus on Eastern European countries that often lack access to relevant information.

The data was produced on behalf of the Copernicus Climate Change Service.

To the right of the text is a map titled "Tmax Brussels Summer 2008-2017". The map shows a color-coded distribution of maximum temperature (Tmax) in Brussels during the summer of 2008-2017. The colors range from blue (cooler) to red (warmer). A legend in the bottom right corner of the map indicates the temperature scale in Kelvin (K), with values 293.0 and 296.5.

Figure 3. Copernicus service example (Copernicus Climate Change Service 2020).

In summary, a typical Copernicus service needs to check the box on the following elements (according to our understanding):

- Proven user interest and added value
- Pan-European or global results
- Clear link to Copernicus input data
- Proven (published) and validated methodology

3 CURE SERVICE PERSPECTIVES

In this Chapter, we assess the status of the CURE applications in light of the typical Copernicus service elements listed in the previous subchapter. The information listed here is derived from the responses of all service providers to the WP6 questionnaire (Annex A).

3.1 User and added value perspective

3.1.1 Background

CURE deliverable D1.1 (Summary of User Requirements) highlights the user needs for spatial and developmental planning in order to address sustainability, resilience and the key political concerns of European cities; including climate change, urban health, economic development, biodiversity loss, etc. This territory management is specified in a variety of policy strategies including mitigation and adaptation actions that enhance the resilience of cities, and support the definition of transition pathways to sustainable and carbon neutral cities. These policy strategies seek sound understanding and quantification of the drivers of urban transition, to support effective policy responses concerning urban vulnerability, and climate change, as defined in various policy commitments including the Urban Agenda of the EU, and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

All of this presents major challenges for urban planners and politicians, as cities are extremely complex systems and the various drivers of change, impacts and responses are strongly interrelated, supporting and competing with each other. Indeed, the effective governance of the cities and city-regions of Europe today is fundamentally undermined by this urban complexity, whereby the high degree of interconnectedness and multiple interactions between socio-economic and environmental factors in a territorial context create major barriers to the effective implementation of sustainable urban planning and development.

Previous pan-European research and innovation experience has demonstrated the deficiencies in respect of both urban planning process and technology enabled decision support tools, that aim to enhance urban planning. Effective solutions are therefore required that define a major opportunity for the EO community to promote the innovative exploitation of underutilised Copernicus derived data, tools and methodologies in dealing with the multi-dimensional problem of urban sustainability and resilience. Copernicus service evolution has been mostly organised in thematic silos so far, and the potential for new products and services, especially as regards cross-cutting cases, is not yet realised and needs to be further exploited. Central to this aim is the need for cross-cutting tools, methods and intelligence linking the complex socio-economic and environmental dimensions of sustainability and resilience in urban planning and development.

3.1.2 Current status of the CURE services

Deliverable D1.1 also presents an analysis of the stakeholder survey from a wider audience and requirements from the CURE front-runner cities. This analysis shows interest in different CURE applications from different types of stakeholders. Both Figure 4 and Figure 5 indicate a range of potential users, who can benefit from the CURE applications. Figure 4 depicts the main expertise domains of participants in the survey; while Figure 5 depicts the domains of the participants, who stated different domain from the predefined options, but they have shown interest for specific CURE applications.

Figure 4. Expertise domain of users participated in the requirements survey.

Figure 5. "Others" expertise and interest in the CURE applications.

Preliminary analysis of the requirements identified in the D1.1 indicates that users and stakeholders showed interest in all CURE applications, with varying levels depending on the background of the stakeholders.

As a first assessment of the added value of the CURE applications, in comparison to related existing services, we rely on the replies to the questionnaires included in Appendix A. This aspect will be investigated in more detail in the following Deliverables of WP6.

The table below provides a short summary of the user and added value aspects of the CURE applications.

Table 1. Overview of the Applications user and added value status.

	<i>REPORTED USER INTEREST</i>	<i>ADDED VALUE</i>
APP01 Local scale surface temperature dynamics	Yes	Use case unclear
APP02 Surface UHI assessment	Yes	Use case unclear
APP03 Urban heat emissions monitoring	Yes	Use case unclear
APP04 Urban CO2 emissions monitoring	Yes	Use case unclear
APP05 Urban flood risk	Yes	Similar to other services available
APP06 Urban subsidence, movements and deformation risk	Yes	Use case clear
APP07 Urban air quality	Yes	Many similar services
APP08 Urban thermal comfort	Yes	Use case clear
APP09 Urban heat storage monitoring	Yes	Use case unclear
APP10 Nature-based solutions	Yes	Use case broad. For the potential off green roofs, the use case is clear
APP11 Health impacts	Yes	Use case clear, health cost of AQ

3.1.3 Recommendations for future developments

D1.1 identifies a few common denominators; which, if followed, will increase the usefulness of the CURE applications across other European cities. These common denominators are:

- CURE should provide the necessary building blocks for the development of downstream cross-cutting applications for impact assessment, urban planning and policy making. Extending the CURE applications for cause-effect analysis can truly unleash the CURE applications potential for the end user community. For example, extending the Nature-Based Solutions (i.e. green roofs) application to other green aspects; such as green infrastructures, trees and their impact on climate (e.g., air quality, CO₂ emissions, floods, heat stress, etc.) and health (e.g., quality of life, short-term and long-term diseases and economic impact); can be greatly received by the user community.
- CURE applications should support varying spatial resolution scales, i.e. from city-region to city and neighbourhood scale by investigating suitable downscaling methods. Overall, there is quite a significant demand for high-resolution data output from the CURE services; from a few meters to 100 meters.
- Most CURE applications should support hourly, daily and annual monitoring information. Furthermore, it was also suggested that the CURE applications should provide information on day / night peaks.
- CURE applications should provide easy access to final products (e.g., WMS), as well as the underlying data by applying various data access methods (e.g., WFS, APIs, file downloads, etc.).
- CURE should act as an easy-to-use platform for data search and access from different Copernicus services.
- CURE applications should provide the basis to perform retrospective modelling and analysis to develop predictive and futuristic models for cities in addressing environmental issues.

From CURE perspective, it is important to find a right balance between harmonised solutions (including temporally and spatially consistent information) across various cities and more tailor made solution to fill specific needs, i.e. deploying more data from cities and developing specific products for specific needs. There is always space for the development of more effective solutions combining EO data with in-situ data (e.g., socio-economic, mobility, etc.). Furthermore, the design of these solutions should be extendable and let researchers and cities extend and build innovative solutions, which can further fulfil local policy and planning needs.

The cross-cutting aspects of the CURE applications should provide the basis for an integrated impact assessment and implementation monitoring capabilities that secure policy co-benefits in relation to Compact Cities and Nature-Based Solutions, Health and Well-being, as well as policy initiatives concerning Mobility and Quality of Life and Cycling/Walking. Such city-focused downstream applications also act as pilots to set the basis for further transferability and downstream services development. This process also assists in filling existing gaps in the

current Copernicus offer in relation to urban areas, and aims to identify to what extent new observation requirements for space borne instruments are needed to realise or improve the specified applications.

3.2 Scale Perspective (Replication potential)

There are two tendencies with respect to scalability (replication) potential of CURE applications which may be contradictory, but also complementary:

- the aim to **prepare services in a maximally universal way** so these can be used by as many cities as possible (ideally in a fully automated manner). This aspect is strongly supported by the fact that the CURE applications are primarily using the Copernicus C3S datasets as the input data.
- the aim to **tailor the services depending on specific requirements of the cities** so they can meet the needs of each city as much as possible

Obviously, it is not possible to fulfil both of these goals and we need to find a reasonable balance. We think the right way to deal with this “contradiction” is to implement the services in a universal way to some extent - to be able to cover a large number of cities. This will need to identify universal requirements of the cities taking also into consideration feasibility, defined by technical character and potential limitations of each of the CURE applications. Taking into consideration the character of the CURE project, we will primarily focus on this universality of services, and the automation of the implementation chain, in order to maximise upscaling potential of the apps. However, although the CURE project is not primarily aiming at downstream services, full “downstream” potential of CURE applications can also be demonstrated, at least on few examples represented by selected applications and cities. In the context of these examples, we will prepare highly tailor-made solutions meeting maximally specific local requirements and priorities, even though these will not be replicable for many other cities.

3.2.1 Aspects of replication potential of the CURE applications

In general, there are several aspects influencing scalability/replicability of CURE applications:

- Copernicus input data needed (character and availability)
- Third-party input data needed (availability and differences in local data)
- End-user requirements (universal versus city-specific)
- Specific scalability potential (different for each of CURE applications, depends mainly on technical character of app, level of automation, data pre-processing, manual work needed, etc.)

Firstly, the replication potential is substantially supported by the fact that most of the inputs for CURE applications are represented by datasets coming from the Copernicus Core Services, which are being regularly produced in a fully harmonized way (mostly on operational basis) for

the European cities and city-regions. Thanks to this, most of the CURE apps will be easily replicable for the vast majority of larger European cities with possibility for regular update in the future, corresponding with the regular update of the Copernicus CS datasets.

Existing Copernicus services are not only dedicated to various thematic domains, but are also targeting different geographical scales (levels of spatial detail) – from a very local through European to global. These target scales are directly linked to the extent of the spatial coverage of different Copernicus services/datasets, while some of them are providing monitoring with seamless global (CAMS, C3S) or often European coverage (e.g. HRLs, Corine CLC), and others are only covering some specific areas of interest, i.e. typically cities or wider city-regions (Urban Atlas for 785 Functional Urban Areas (FUA) for the 2018 reference year in EEA39 countries, Urban Atlas building heights, etc.). Moreover, the availability of the Urban Atlas is limited only to larger European cities (more than 100.000 inhabitants) and its availability also differs depending on the reference years (which is also related to changes in FUA definition for European cities during last years).

Secondly, the replicability of the CURE applications may differ depending on timescale/year of interest of analysis, which is of interest of the user. The major advantage is that most of the Copernicus datasets are produced on regular basis and their production is secured also for the near future. Most of the CLMS dataset are produced in regular time periods (typically 3 or 6 years (e.g. 3 for HRL Imperviousness, 6 for Urban Atlas), so they are not available for the intervals between production dates; while the C3S, CAMS, or CEMS are regularly updated in a near-real-time manner, on daily or even hourly bases, depending on the type and source of the data and specific dataset.

For the replication potential in the future, the Copernicus programme represents an extremely safe and robust basis of the input data production for CURE applications. This, at least, is valid for the European cities, while the replication potential is limited for the non-European cities, where some of the Copernicus data – in particular those from the CLMS - are not available at all. For such cities, the CURE apps can only be replicated in case the originally required Copernicus CS input datasets will be replaced with relevant datasets of similar character, covering those cities; which may be made available by the city administrations (e.g. planning and environmental agencies) or may be produced by dedicated mapping services (e.g. GISAT is producing detailed Urban Atlas such as LC mapping layers for some non-European cities). Such data, in case the nomenclature will be harmonised with the Copernicus one, may replace the Copernicus input data, if those are not available, which gives some replication potential for the CURE applications even outside Europe.

In contrast with strong replication potential of the CURE apps coming from the Copernicus CS input datasets, the replication potential may be weakened in case that some of the CURE apps

will have to be fed by **local city data**, needed as an additional, but still necessary input. With respect to the local input data, there are, in general, two main limitation factors:

- Availability of input datasets required
- Different character of local input data among different cities

The main limitation related to the local data is that some of the input data needed by CURE applications may not be available in some cities. This, obviously, will disable replicability of that particular CURE app for those cities and the only way to implement this app for such cities will be to prepare the input datasets needed by the CURE (or external) service providers (e.g. via mapping, laser scanning, measuring, etc.).

Another probably more frequent limitation is that the CURE service providers will have to deal with different character (formats, nomenclatures, etc.) of the local input data among different cities. These differences may disable automated input of these local datasets into CURE applications running on the CURE system (on DIAS) and may lead to need for manual editing at certain level to transform such datasets into a form readable by CURE applications. This will not disable replicability, but will complicate or limit it to a certain extent.

Some of the CURE applications may also need other types of third-party input data than the local/city ones, e.g. Open Street Maps (OSM) features or World Surface Footprint data. Those datasets are typically available with global coverage, which is also an important advantage for the replication potential outside Europe. However, the OSM coverage may be limited or its reliability may not be acceptable in some cities or parts of them, which has to be strongly taken into consideration for the CURE apps using the OSM features as input data.

The next aspect, which needs to be considered when assessing the replication potential of CURE applications, is the character of end-user requirements. In some cases, these can be quite universal, common across most European cities, which, again, strengthens the replication potential of the respective app. However, in other cases, “typical” requirements of the CURE pilot cities on some of the CURE apps could be rather city-specific and irrelevant to other cities. As the general aim of the CURE project is more to focus on universality and generality of the applications strengthening their replication (or upscaling) potential to as many European cities as possible, the service providers need to carefully assess the requirements of pilot cities. The requirements, identified as general (expected to be common among cities), are of top priority and should be certainly addressed. On the other hand, several city-specific requirements may not be (fully) addressed, as the CURE project does not aim to prepare downstream services. However, the downstream potential of CURE apps should be definitely taken into consideration for the future, while designing the CURE apps.

The last but not least aspect is the specific scalability potential of each of the CURE applications (depends mainly on the technical character, level of automation, data pre-processing, manual work needed, etc.). This aspect is addressed in detail in the next subchapter.

Table 2. Scalability potential of CURE applications as seen by application developers.

	<i>Can be easily deployed for many cities (in Europe)</i>	<i>Can be easily deployed for many cities (outside Europe)</i>	<i>Non-Copernicus input data needed</i>
APP01 Local scale surface temperature dynamics	Yes	Possible, but more difficult	No
APP02 Surface UHI assessment	Yes (linked to APP01)	Possible, but more difficult	No
APP03 Urban heat emissions monitoring	Possible (linked to APP01)	No	HR building and tree models
APP04 Urban CO2 emissions monitoring	No	No	Specific local measurements
APP05 Urban flood risk	Yes	Possible, but more difficult	Local hydrology information
APP06 Urban subsidence, movements and deformation risk	Yes	Possible, but more difficult	No
APP07 Urban air quality	Yes	Possible, but more difficult	HR building model
APP08 Urban thermal comfort	Yes	Possible, but more difficult	HR building and tree models
APP09 Urban heat storage monitoring	No	No	Specific local measurements
APP10 Nature-based solutions	Possible	Possible, but more difficult	Lidar, HR building model, building cadastre info
APP11 Health impacts	Yes	No	Local air quality and population statistics

The summary on scalability potential of each particular CURE application (coming from the Questionnaires presented in Appendix A of this document) is presented in Table 2. For 9 of 11

CURE applications, there is a decent scalability potential, although in some cases it may be partly limited due to availability of local data input (e.g. APP03, APP10). Only for the APP04, the service provider indicated that it is not scalable at the moment and its scalability potential is low for the future. Similarly, the scalability potential of APP09 has been described as “very difficult” by its provider.

3.2.2 Efforts needed to enhance replication potential

The fact that the CURE services are built on Copernicus CS datasets is one of the key steps to secure the replicability/scalability of the CURE applications.

Another crucial aspect to ease the future replicability of the CURE applications is to automatize the apps as much as possible in order to mitigate the manual efforts needed to be able to run the apps for new cities (or time horizons) in the future. This includes the necessities of direct linking with the Copernicus input data as stored in dedicated repositories and automatically transferring these datasets to the CURE system (running on DIAS), where they will serve as the inputs for calculations implemented in the frame of the CURE applications.

For the (in particular local) third party data, proper harmonization of the expected data inputs for each of the applications is also required, in the sense of needing specification of the format, nomenclature, etc. Without this process, the third-party data cannot be ingested into CURE applications in an automated manner. These standardised formats have to be properly specified by the developer of each application, to be able to transfer these requirements effectively to the end-users.

In general, the existence of the CURE system accommodating all the CURE applications is crucial for the replication potential of the CURE applications, as it will allow to easily access and run the applications for any new city when needed.

3.3 IT Perspective

3.3.1 Current status of the CURE applications

As mentioned in the previous subchapter, an important aspect in the scalability potential of the CURE applications are the IT aspects (technical character of the applications, level of automation, data pre-processing, storage needs, etc.). As this is also very important information to ensure a good understanding and cooperation between Work Package 3 and 4 of the CURE project, we have devoted specific attention to this perspective in the WP6 questionnaire. The summary of the most relevant information related to the scalability potential regarding the IT perspective is listed in table below.

Table 3. IT aspects related to scalability potential of the CURE applications

	<i>Input data</i>	<i>Interim storage (per city)</i>	<i>Output data storage (per city)</i>
APP01 Local scale surface temperature dynamics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic Surface Cover Fractions (100 m) • Representative emissivity for each surface cover type • Thermal infrared (TIR) measurements (1 km) • Atmospheric information (water vapour) 	/	100s MB's
APP02 Surface UHI assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CLMS HR Imperviousness 2018 • Land Surface Temperature from APP01 • perhaps L2A (<60%cc) or yearly NDVI-Max 	< 10 GB	Some MB's
APP03 Urban heat emissions monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LST from APP01 • high resolution LULC map • high resolution DOMs (trees and buildings) • standard meteorology • Flux tower data 	Not known yet	<1MB
APP04 Urban CO2 emissions monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High resolution LULC map • high resolution DOMs (trees and buildings) • standard meteorology • Diurnal/seasonal courses)of source strengths • Flux tower data • Footprint climatology 	Not known yet	1 GB
APP05 Urban flood risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • terrain model • river network layer • hydrological data on extreme rainfall events • meteorological data on extreme rainfall events • a land use map (different urban land uses) • Copernicus satellite imageries + VHR 	GB's	100s MB's

<p>APP06 Urban subsidence, movements and deformation risk</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ground deformations (Copernicus EGMS / Results from custom interferometric analysis) • Land use (Copernicus Urban atlas / Custom land use map) • Built-up expansion (WSF-Evo / GHSL) 	<p>1s-10s GB's (excluding custom MT InSAR chain)</p> <p>-</p> <p>1s-10s TB's (including custom MT InSAR chain)</p>	<p>10s-100s MB</p>
<p>APP07 Urban air quality</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CAMS: air quality reanalysis data • CAMS: air pollutant emissions • CLMS: Urban Atlas building height • OSM: building locations and roadmap • C3S: 2m temperature and 10m (vectorial) wind speed • EIONET: Point Source emissions reported for LRTAP convention 	<p>30 GB</p>	<p>200MB</p>
<p>APP08 Urban thermal comfort</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UrbClim meteorological variables (100 m) • VHR land use map 	<p>1 GB</p>	<p>100s MB's</p>
<p>APP09 Urban heat storage monitoring</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamim surface temperature (from App01) • Dynamic Surface Cover Fractions (100m) • 3D information on the buildings and trees height • Net-all wave radiation flux • Time rate of change for net all-wave radiation at the surface • Coefficients associated to response of the surface cover due the energy input 	<p>0</p>	<p>100s MB's</p>

APP10 Nature-based solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• LiDAR,• Euro Maps 3D• DSM generated by DLR (tri-stereo imagery)• NDVI• Imperviousness• Albedo• Cadastre information (year of construction and protection level)	10s GB's	100s MB's
APP11 Health impacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Air quality data from Sofia	Not known yet	Not known yet

3.3.2 Efforts needed during the CURE project and beyond

First, a lot of different input data seems to be required. Although all DIAS platforms contain a lot of Copernicus data, several sources need to get uploaded. After deciding on which DIAS the CURE system will run and depending on its set of Copernicus data, responsible WP2 partner GISAT needs to upload the missing input data.

Furthermore, it seems that a lot of this input data is preprocessed, so it needs to be decided if the preprocessing tasks are part of the service workflows or if the data needs to get preprocessed beforehand.

The hardware requirements (CPU's and RAM) could not be specified in this phase for all the applications. Therefore, this will have to be resolved early in the next phase in order to avoid memory errors from the virtual machines hosting the applications in the CURE System.

To ensure an easy and smooth integration of the application into the infrastructure, some preconditions have to be met:

- To share and version the code a distributed version-control system is needed. Every application should be contained in a repository. The repository must only contain code, tests and docker instructions.
- To deploy the application, it must be dockerised. The dockerisation of the application allows it to run on any machine independently. Optionally a deploy pipeline can fasten up the process of deployment.
- To instruct the application with the right parameters, an execution command must be provided. Additionally, the input data that is needed for the application to run must be provided. This data can be either raw data or pre-processed data. If the application consists of more than one execution the order and parallelism need to be given.

- To start the application via the API, a list of parameters must be given. As a quality check some content and regex-checks should be added.

Furthermore, to ensure the quality of code, maintainability and fail safeness some implementations to the code of the application are mandatory.

- To maintain the code logging should be used. GeoVille provides an API and a python library to log to the central logging system.
- To fasten up integration and fail safeness the code needs to be tested by several unit-tests.

To prepare the infrastructure some next steps need to be decided:

- Which distributed version-control system (Git, Bitbucket, etc.) is going to be used?
- Who provides and prepares the pre-processed data that is needed by the applications?
- Missing hardware information should be added to the questionnaire.
- The consortium needs to decide which DIAS is going to be used. As soon as this decision is made, GeoVille can start to set up the infrastructure on the respective DIAS.

4 CURE SCENARIOS FOR INTEGRATION IN COPERNICUS

After the detailed assessment of the CURE applications in the previous Chapter, we can assess the overall status of the CURE applications in light of the typical Copernicus service elements, listed in Chapter 2 (Proven user interest and added value, Pan-European or global results, Clear link to Copernicus input data, and Proven (published) and validated methodology). An overview of the current status of the CURE applications is shown in Table 4.

For all the 11 CURE applications, there is reported interest from users and/or stakeholders of the project. However, when it comes to the added value of the services in regard to similar services that are available on the market, the use case is not unique or clear yet for 7 of the 11 applications. This does not have to limit their potential for uptake as a CURE service, but some efforts might be needed to convince Copernicus of their added value.

Of the 11 CURE applications, 9 indicate that they should be more or less straightforward to upscale them (implementing them to plenty of European cities. As most of them rely on European datasets (e.g. Urban Atlas) that are available for many cities in Europe, this aspect could be covered in a rather limited time after the end of the CURE project. Clearly, going beyond Europe is difficult for all applications, as the needed input data is not readily available. The upscaling should thus best focus on European cities in the first instance.

Of the 11 CURE applications, all are using Copernicus data as input (which was a project requirement), but only 3 are based uniquely on Copernicus data sets, enabling them very straightforward to be deployed in a Copernicus context. 6 applications need more detailed local data as input for their services, complicating their implementation in a Copernicus context. Finally, 2 applications are heavily dependent on specific local measurements, which hampers their use in a Copernicus context.

Of the 11 CURE applications, 6 are based on published methodologies. Most applications are used in research contexts, and some operationalisation steps are needed before deploying them. However, the number one goal of the CURE project is to get the application methodologies operational, validated against measurements, and published. So, this aspect should not be a limiting factor for the uptake as a Copernicus service.

Table 4. Overview of the Applications potential for Copernicus. Colors indicate if the requirement is met (green), if it can be met with some effort (yellow) or if it is extremely difficult to be met (red).

	User interest and added value	Scalability	Non-Copernicus data needed	Proven methodology
APP01 Local scale surface temperature dynamics	Use case unclear	Yes	No	Yes
APP02 Surface UHI assessment	Use case unclear	Yes	No	No
APP03 Urban heat emissions monitoring	Use case unclear	Local data input required	HR building and tree models	Yes
APP04 Urban CO2 emissions monitoring	Use case unclear	Service not yet ready for upscaling	Specific local measurements	No
APP05 Urban flood risk	Similar to other services available	Yes	Local hydrology information	No
APP06 Urban subsidence, movements and deformation risk	Use case clear	Yes	No	No
APP07 Urban air quality	Many similar services	Yes	HR building model	Yes
APP08 Urban thermal comfort	Use case clear	Yes	HR building and tree models	Yes
APP09 Urban heat storage monitoring	Use case unclear	Very difficult	Specific local measurements	Yes
APP10 Nature-based solutions	Use case broad. For the potential for green roofs the use case is clear	Local data input required	Lidar, HR building model, building cadastre info	No
APP11 Health impacts	Use case clear	Yes	Local air quality and population statistics	Yes

Based on this information, alternative scenarios can be defined concerning the CURE uptake in the Copernicus framework. The assessment and the final selection of the proper scenario(s) will mainly depend on the progress made during the CURE project; and the future evolution of Copernicus, where the concrete implementation of the Copernicus Knowledge Hubs is still unclear. It will be very important to keep a close eye on these evolutions during the course of the project, and establish a relationship with the responsible of the Sustainable Urban Development Hub, in which the CURE system would logically fit, as soon as possible.

4.1 Scenario 1: Rapid implementation of a slim CURE service

A demonstration service will be promptly set up including the applications that are most ready to be transformed into a Copernicus service, as a basis for discussion and negotiations. In this context, a Copernicus urban entry point will be created redirecting to the separate CURE applications, which will be positioned under an existing Copernicus core service. Logical candidates to be included in this “slim” CURE service are the ones having none or only 1 non-green field in Table 4 (e.g. APP01, APP06 and APP08). It would be best to prioritise these applications in the WP4 developments, as they are probably most suited for a quick roll-out. Furthermore, one (or more) of these applications can be quickly upscaled (within the CURE project) to a large number of European cities (even beyond the front-runner and follower cities of the CURE project) to showcase the scalability potential of the service. The focus in this scenario is on the applications that can be applied in a fully automated manner for as many cities as possible. This aspect is strongly supported with the fact that these CURE applications are primarily using the Copernicus core services datasets as their input data.

4.2 Scenario 2: Extended in-depth CURE service

CURE prototype will evolve into a new (urban) Copernicus core service including all (or as many as possible) CURE applications, which will have been developed addressing all issues (presented in the yellow and red cells of Table 4) during (or after) the CURE project and before their roll-out. The new Copernicus core service will be able to support all stakeholders (scientists, planners, decision makers, etc.), who seek to handle challenges closely related to urban resilience and sustainability, displaying its inclusiveness. Moreover, some of these applications will be tailored to meet the specific requirements of the cities as much as possible (e.g. APP03, APP05, APP07, APP10 and APP11). These applications can showcase the full “downstream” potential of the CURE service by maximally meeting specific local requirements and priorities, even though these will not be easily replicable for many other cities.

4.3 Scenario 3: Cross-cutting and interactive CURE service

The potential of the CURE service for users and stakeholders will be maximized by the development of downstream cross-cutting applications for impact assessment, urban planning and decision/policy making. Although these aspects go beyond the proposed work of the CURE

project, the framework and workflow can be discussed and agreed upon during the CURE project. Thus, the CURE service will integrate these aspects into its development as a Copernicus core or complementary (“slim”) service, including (almost) all or the more suitable applications, respectively. Extending the CURE applications for cause-effect analysis can truly unleash the CURE applications potential for the end user community. For example, extending the Nature-Based Solutions (i.e. green roofs) application to other green interventions such as pocket gardens, planted fences etc., as well as monitoring and evaluating their impacts on environmental (e.g. air quality, CO₂ emissions, floods, heat stress, etc.) and socio-economic (e.g. quality of life, short-term and long-term diseases and economic impact) urban features would be greatly received by the user community. This process also assists in filling existing gaps in the current Copernicus offer in relation to urban areas, and aims to identify to what extent new EO requirements for space borne instruments are needed to realise or improve the specified applications.

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APPENDIX A: QUESTIONNAIRES TO SERVICE PROVIDERS

Ap01 Local scale surface temperature dynamics

Question 1: Describe your service-to-be in technical detail (include schemes if possible), while addressing the sub-questions.

The CURE Local Scale Surface Temperature Dynamics App to be developed by FORTH, is aiming at time series of urban surface temperature maps in local scale based on Copernicus Data. The surface temperature is one of the most important parameters in the physical processes of urban surface energy, water balance and the land-atmosphere exchanges. In this context, this CURE application will be utilized in all urban areas involved in the project, leading to frequent local scale surface temperature estimations, which are essential data for other CURE applications, i.e. the Surface Urban Heat Island (UHI) Assessment application, the Urban Heat Emissions Monitoring application and the Urban Heat Storage Monitoring application.

The surface temperature retrieval will be based on a downscaling algorithm (Mitraka et al., 2015^[1]) which downscales Copernicus Sentinel-3 thermal data of 1 km spatial resolution to 100 m spatial resolution, using surface cover information of higher spatial resolution. In CURE the surface cover information will be retrieved from Sentinel-2 and combined CLMS information. Ancillary information from spectral libraries is used for the estimation of urban emissivity and atmospheric information from C3S for the atmospheric correction in the thermal infrared.

^[1] Mitraka, Z., Chrysoulakis, N., Doxani, G., Del Frate, F., Berger, M., 2015. Urban Surface Temperature Time Series Estimation at the Local Scale by Spatial-Spectral Unmixing of Satellite Observations. *Remote Sens.* 7, 4139–4156. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs70404139>

- **What data does your service need?**
 - Dynamic Surface Cover Fractions in 100 m spatial resolution
 - Representative emissivity for each surface cover type
 - Thermal infrared (TIR) measurements (1 km)
 - Atmospheric information (water vapour) matching the TIR satellite acquisition time.
- **Does your code run with raw input data or does it require preprocessed data?**

The code does not run with raw Copernicus input data, the data need to be preprocessed.

- **How much storage does your interim and output data need? (Please provide two sizes, one for interim and one for output data)**

For each city:

The app will not probably not produce any interim data.

As output data the code produces a Geotiff files with a typical size in the order of a few hundred Mb.

- **Does your service contain more than one task (series of script executions)?**

For the moment yes, it is a series of several scripts, but we aim to build it into a single script with several functions.

- **What resources does your service need for processing one unit (Cores, RAM)?**

The codes run on a single core with 16 (or more) Gb RAM and runs for a few seconds to minutes (depending on the domain size).

- **Do you use Docker?**

No, we will use Docker for the first time in CURE.

Question 2: Will your service be user-interactive (how?) or do you only provide output data/maps?

It will only provide output urban surface temperature maps.

We can definitely discuss this with the users, but it is highly unlikely that they want to adjust the model parameters. It would require specific scientific knowledge.

Question 3: How do you see your service evolve on the long term (after the CURE project)?

We aim to continue this work after the CURE project and integrate the service in the Copernicus framework. The urban temperature service can be used in each of these cities to make local scale surface temperature time series maps.

Question 4: What is the added value for scientists/urban stakeholders over existing services?

- Is there any commercial service available in the market that provides a similar solution? (i.e. which are the main "competitor services" offering alternative solutions to yours)? (Note: please list the "applications")
- What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to your service?
- Do you know any new service in progress of development (with TRL 7 or 8) that could compete in the future with your service?

Land surface temperature (LST) products are available from the CLMS^[1] but in low spatial resolution (~5 km) which makes them inappropriate for use for urban sites. Similarly, LST products are available in high spatial resolution from satellite missions like Landsat^[2] and ASTER^[3], but these provide low temporal resolution.

This CURE application will provide dynamic (high temporal resolution) local scale surface temperature (of high spatial resolution, 100 m) maps, with algorithms designed for the retrieval of urban temperature (accounting for the variability of urban materials).

- Strengths of existing services compared to the CURE service:
 - Operational algorithms easily applicable globally
- Weaknesses of existing services compared to the CURE service:
 - Algorithms designed for retrieval of urban surface temperature, accounting for the variability of the urban materials
 - Local scale estimations of urban surface temperature
 - Capturing the diurnal variation of urban surface temperature in local scale

There are several publications and scientific projects towards the direction (e.g. Zhang et al., 2013^[4]), but no services available from those.

^[1] <https://land.copernicus.eu/global/products/lst>

^[2] http://rslab.gr/downloads_LandsatLST.html

^[3] https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/products/ast_08v003/

^[4] Zhan, W., Chen, Y., Zhou, J., Wang, J., Liu, W., Voogt, J., Zhu, X., Quan, J., Li, J., 2013. Disaggregation of remotely sensed land surface temperature: Literature survey, taxonomy, issues, and caveats. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 131, 119–139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2012.12.014>

Question 5: How easily can your service be upscaled to other cities (both in Europe and outside Europe)?

The method is transferable to every city, with the limitation of spectral library data for representative emissivity values and given that detailed land cover maps are available. For European cities where Urban Atlas data are available the method is easily transferable, assuming that the London spectral library data of urban materials is appropriate for the rest of

European cities. With specific assumptions, or a more advanced approach on emissivity retrieval for cities worldwide, the service could operate on a global scale.

Question 6: Is your service linked with existing Copernicus services?

Yes, C3S and CLMS => see scheme above

Ap02 Surface Urban Heat Island Assessment

Question 1: Describe your service-to-be in technical detail (include schemes if possible), while addressing the sub-questions.

App02 aims at estimating the Surface Urban Heat Island Intensity (SUHII) by exploiting (and possibly further improving) the methodology recently presented by Li et al. (2018). In particular, the intended approach will allow to calculate SUHII (and its temporal dynamics) by exploiting the linear relationship between Land Surface Temperature (LST) and the percentage impervious surface (PIS), which – according to the literature - proved consistent for cities in biomes dominated by forests and grasslands as in Europe.

Linear functions of LST is well fitted using ISA that regionalized by a KDE method (ISA_{KDE}). Slope of the functions is defined as the surface urban heat island intensity.

- What data does your service need?

The service requires as input the CLMS HR Imperviousness layer for the year 2018, as well as the Land Surface Temperature product generated in the framework of App01 (by exploiting both CLMS and CAMS products as input) both in GeoTiff format (the former at 10m resolution; the latter at 100m resolution).

Alternatively/complementary to the above, we are testing the effectiveness of employing an improved and updated imperviousness product derived from multitemporal Sentinel-2 imagery. In that case, one would need to gather all Level-2A Surface Reflectance S2 scenes with nominal cloud coverage lower than 60% intersecting the given area of interest in the entire target year and compute the maximum temporal NDVI for each pixel.

- **Does your code run with raw input data or does it require preprocessed data?**

Both.

- **How much storage does your interim and output data need? (Please provide two sizes, one for interim and one for output data)**

The envisaged output is a single number quantifying the SUHII for the given city of interest in the given time-frame and as such is in the range of few MBs. The interim storage varies with the size of the targeted area of interest and the input data sources, but should likely not exceed 10GB in the case where S2 data have to be processed.

- **Does your service contain more than one task (series of script executions)?**

This is still under development, but highly likely yes if, ultimately, we rely on an existing open software for part of the processing (e.g., simple geometrical operations with gdal, linear or empirical regression using the libsvm or pksvm tools) and own python scripts for the remaining.

- **What resources does your service need for processing one unit (Cores, RAM)?**

Unfortunately, we cannot be very precise at this time here. Nevertheless, we envisage the whole process to be particularly fast and light; indeed, we are dealing with relatively small-size input GeoTiff images and a series of simple tasks to be executed. In the hypothesis that the maximum temporal NDVI has to be computed out of S2 imagery, the processing will become (slightly) more intense, with a higher RAM use, but likely well within 4GB.

- **Do you use Docker?**

We have been using them in the past and foresee their employment here as well.

Question 2: Will your service be user-interactive (how?) or do you only provide output data/maps?

Yes, optionally we would like the users to have the possibility of defining their specific area of interest for which to estimate the corresponding SUHII. This should happen ideally by drawing

a polygon or uploading a vector geometry. Additionally, the users should also specify the time frame for which to perform the analysis.

Question 3: How do you see your service evolve on the long term (after the CURE project)?

Ideally, we foresee it to become the reference service for providing SUHII information for any city at European scale. Users should be able to check and compare the current and past SUHII for predefined cities (e.g., the 700+ included in the Urban Atlas), but also to request the computation for specific AOIs at specific times (provided the availability of the App01 LST product).

Question 4: What is the added value for scientists/urban stakeholders over existing services?

- **Is there any commercial service available in the market that provides a similar solution? (i.e. which are the main "competitor services" offering alternative solutions to yours)? (Note: please list the "applications")**

To our knowledge there is not yet any existing comparable service available.

- **What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to your service?**

/

- **Do you know any new service in progress of development (with TRL 7 or 8) that could compete in the future with your service?**

No

Question 5: How easily can your service be upscaled to other cities (both in Europe and outside Europe)?

Upscaling should be straightforward, in the light of the full automation, the limited size of the input data and the envisaged light and fast processing. Given the availability of the HR imperviousness layer, for Europe it will be easier. Outside Europe is feasible, but shall rely then on the S2-based imperviousness only.

Question 6: Is your service linked with existing Copernicus services?

Yes. It is linked to the CLMS service directly and CAMS indirectly through the LST product from App01

Ap03 Urban Heat Emissions Monitoring

Question 1: Describe your service-to-be in technical detail (include schemes if possible), while addressing the sub-questions.

The CURE Urban Heat Emissions App uses the aerodynamic resistance method for calculating sensible heat fluxes as described in Feigenwinter et al. (2018) [\[1\]](#) and CURE Deliverable D1.3 “Methodology review and selection”. A DOM (Digital Object Model) for buildings and trees, Land Surface Temperature and basic meteorological data (Air Temperature, wind velocity, wind direction, air pressure) is needed as input. The output is a map (GeoTiff, 100m resolution) with sensible heat flux values. The output is evaluated with in-situ flux tower data.

[\[1\]](#) FEIGENWINTER, C., VOGT, R., PARLOW, E., LINDBERG, F., MARCONCINI, M., FRATE, F. D. & CHRYSOULAKIS, N. 2018. Spatial Distribution of Sensible and Latent Heat Flux in the City of Basel (Switzerland). IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing, 11, 2717-2723.

- **What data does your service need?**

LST from App01, high resolution LULC map, high resolution DOMs (trees and buildings), standard meteorology (air temperature, humidity, wind, wind direction, pressure, radiation). Flux tower data needed for validation

- **Does your code run with raw input data or does it require preprocessed data?**

The code does not run with raw Copernicus input data, the data need to be preprocessed

- **How much storage does your interim and output data need? (Please provide two sizes, one for interim and one for output data)**

Depending on time period and available scenes for LST (App01). One scene covers the previously defined AOI (area of interest) for all case study cities. In the case of Heraklion this is about 85 km² and one map needs 36 kB of storage capacity.

- **Does your service contain more than one task (series of script executions)?**

No, it consists of one script.

- **What resources does your service need for processing one unit (Cores, RAM)?**

tbd

- **Do you use Docker?**

No

Question 2: Will your service be user-interactive (how?) or do you only provide output data/maps?

The service only provides output data/maps (GeoTiff)

Question 3: How do you see your service evolve on the long term (after the CURE project)?

Possible transferability/generalization to other cities provided the needed input data is available

Question 4: What is the added value for scientists/urban stakeholders over existing services?

Urban heat emission refers to the turbulent sensible heat flux, i.e. the heat exchange between the urban surface and the atmosphere. The sensible heat flux defines the amount of energy that is available for heating the urban atmosphere and it is thus closely related to air temperature. This amount of energy is strongly modified by the properties of the surface (land cover/ land use, 3D geometry) and the input of heat by human activities (traffic, buildings, industry). The localization of hot spots of high heat emissions will help urban planners to optimize their adaption strategies also with regard to heat stress, urban green space and building development.

- **Is there any commercial service available in the market that provides a similar solution? (i.e. which are the main "competitor services" offering alternative solutions to yours)? (Note: please list the "applications")**

There are commercial software packages (e.g. ENVI-met) that can deliver similar maps of sensible heat flux.

- **What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to your service?**

App03 only provides sensible heat fluxes (easy implementation, low cost), while commercial packages may process complete climate simulation (complex implementation and high costs).

- **Do you know any new service in progress of development (with TRL 7 or 8) that could compete in the future with your service?**

No

Question 5: How easily can your service be upscaled to other cities (both in Europe and outside Europe)?

See question 3: Upscaling to other cities depends on the availability of input data.

Question 6: Is your service linked with existing Copernicus services?

CLMS (Urban Atlas and Building heights) if available

C3S Reanalysis data (alternative to in-situ meteorological data as input)

Ap04 Urban CO₂ emissions monitoring

Question 1: Describe your service-to-be in technical detail (include schemes if possible), while addressing the sub-questions.

The CURE Urban CO₂ Emissions App uses a land use regression model (LUR) based on source area weighted and source strength weighted CO₂ fluxes from an urban flux tower for estimating city-wide CO₂ emissions. A detailed high resolution Land Use/Land Cover map, a DOM (Digital Object Model) for buildings and trees, basic meteorological data (Air Temperature, wind velocity, wind direction, air pressure) and profiles of source strengths derived from population density, traffic, vegetation dynamics, etc. are needed as input. The output is a map (GeoTiff, 100m resolution) with CO₂ emissions (anthropogenic and biogenic).

- **What data does your service need?**

High resolution LULC map, high resolution DOMs (trees and buildings), standard meteorology (air temperature, humidity, wind, wind direction, pressure, radiation). Profiles (diurnal/seasonal courses) of source strengths derived from population density, traffic, vegetation dynamics, etc. Flux tower data and a footprint climatology is needed for establishing the regression model and evaluation.

- **Does your code run with raw input data or does it require preprocessed data?**

The data need to be preprocessed

- **How much storage does your interim and output data need? (Please provide two sizes, one for interim and one for output data)**

Depending on time period. One scene covers the previously defined AOI (area of interest) for all case study cities. In the case of Heraklion this is about 85 km² and one map needs 36 kB of storage capacity. To document CO₂ emissions for one year (total and seasonal mean diurnal courses) a storage capacity of about 1 GB is estimated.

- **Does your service contain more than one task (series of script executions)?**

tbd

- **What resources does your service need for processing one unit (Cores, RAM)?**

tbd

- **Do you use Docker?**

No

Question 2: Will your service be user-interactive (how?) or do you only provide output data/maps?

Output data/maps (GeoTiff)

Question 3: How do you see your service evolve on the long term (after the CURE project)?

The service will be in any case a prototype which has to be further developed. Transferability to other cities may be given in a later stage provided the needed input data is available (flux tower needed!)

Question 4: What is the added value for scientists/urban stakeholders over existing services?

The total urban CO₂ emissions have a spatial dimension due to the heterogeneous nature of urban land use/land cover and urbanization. In this CURE application, the CO₂ emissions are partitioned into an anthropogenic (traffic, heating/cooling) and a biogenic component (urban green space). Spatial planning strategies have an influence on the urban form, and consequently affect CO₂ emissions through changes in traffic patterns, energy consumption and location and extent of urban green areas. Knowing the portion of the anthropogenic and the biogenic part of CO₂ emissions in a high spatial resolution (neighborhood scale) will provide urban planners with an additional decision support tool for developing emission reduction strategies.

- **Is there any commercial service available in the market that provides a similar solution? (i.e. which are the main "competitor services" offering alternative solutions to yours)? (Note: please list the "applications")**

Not to our knowledge

- **What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to your service?**

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- **Do you know any new service in progress of development (with TRL 7 or 8) that could compete in the future with your service?**

No.

Question 5: How easily can your service be upscaled to other cities (both in Europe and outside Europe)?

See question 3: The application will not be mature enough to be upscaled to other cities.

Question 6: Is your service linked with existing Copernicus services?

CLMS (Urban Atlas) if available

CAMS (GHG fluxes) for validation

C3S (in-situ observations) meteorological data

Ap05 Urban Flood Risk

Question 1: Describe your service-to-be in technical detail (include schemes if possible), while addressing the sub-questions.

The CURE **AP05 - Urban Flood Risk** modelling service will combine hydrological modelling approaches, satellite data and overlay analysis to obtain information about exposure of urban features to potential floods.

Flood hazard exposure is achieved by combination of various means:

(i) flood inundation extent and frequency from historical EO data, (ii) geomorphic analysis using DEM/DSM for estimation of flood susceptibility, (iii) modelling inundation extent and depth using runoff and discharge patterns, morphology and land cover.

There are few options for hydrological modelling itself and estimation of magnitude of floods. All of them are based on open source codes SW packages (with different types of licensing). The most suitable solution for CURE 05 app will be selected based on user requirements and technical specifications. In previous implementations, GISAT used the Hec-RAS (US Army Hydrologic Engineering Center) or Flo-2D (US Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) supported) SW suites for hydrological modelling. However, also the Anuga and OpenFOAM will be considered to be used for this purposes. All these models are based on combination of local terrain morphology and hydrological characteristics with intensity of precipitation and runoff during extreme rainfall events. Based on this, the expected magnitude of flood (extent, inundation depth) is modelled for scenarios of flood events with different magnitudes.

Additionally, this modelling approach based on hydrological models will be complemented by an approach based on Copernicus satellite data, taking into consideration flood events in the past and estimating flood probability (susceptibility) for each location inside the area of interest.

The main result of the modelling will be the maps showing flood extent, inundation depth or flood susceptibility for different magnitude of potential flood events (represented by specific intensity of rainfall and runoff). Additionally, flood risk to urban features/community assets will be estimated, combining the results of flood scenario modelling with the information about geographical distribution of urban features, coming from land use maps (Copernicus Urban Atlas or local urban planning maps). Flood hazard to population can be also modelled, based on known or estimated (e.g. via disaggregation) distribution of dwellers in the city.

Last, but not least, also the rapid flood monitoring information during recent or on-going events can be offered in the frame of this service, if requested by the user.

The results can be either shared as GIS layers in raster or vector format, which can be easily integrated into GIS platform of the city or in a form of maps with proper symbology and legend. However, we prefer to visualize results in an interactive web-based application, allowing the

user to interactively explore and analyze the flood hazard for his city, and in combination with additional relevant data (DTM, land use maps).

- **What data does your service need?**

The service needs detailed terrain model, river network layer and hydrological and meteorological data on extreme rainfall events. Moreover, a land use map is needed, as detailed as possible, distinguishing between different classes of urban land use. The second will be represented by Copernicus Urban Atlas by default and can be complemented by local urban planning maps if available. For the flood analysis based on satellite data, the Copernicus satellite imageries will be used as an input, which can be complemented by additional third-party VHR data for specific dates during or after flood events.

- **Does your code run with raw input data or does it require preprocessed data?**

The code does not run with raw Copernicus input data, the data need to be preprocessed.

- **How much storage does your interim and output data need? (Please provide two sizes, one for interim and one for output data)**

For each city:

As interim data, the results of hydrological modelling are produced. The size depends largely on the chosen domain size, but is typically in the order of a few Gb.

As output data the code produces one or more vector layers files with a typical size in the order of a few hundred Mb.

- **Does your service contain more than one task (series of script executions)?**

Yes it is processing chain composed of several independent SW products.

- **What resources does your service need for processing one unit (Cores, RAM)?**

The used SW products runs on a four core CPU with 16 (or more) Gb RAM and runs for a few hours to a day (depending on the domain size).

- **Do you use Docker?**

GISAT has expertise with dockerization of applications. For this particular app, the feasibility of dockerization needs to be assessed, because of the dependencies on some proprietary SW packages, which, however, may be replaced by other solutions during the implementation process.

Question 2: Will your service be user-interactive (how?) or do you only provide output data/maps?

Yes, service will be user-interactive. User will alter inputs and modelling parameters. This would allow the user to model assess their own flooding scenarios.

Question 3: How do you see your service evolve on the long term (after the CURE project)?

The aim is to develop an application which will be livable after the CURE project ends and will work in an interactive and automated way, allowing the users to add new cities or modify input parameters and model different flood scenarios. This, however, may require some additional efforts still needed after the CURE project is finished, including development of a web-based platform and integration of advanced functionalities allowing user-driven parametrization of the modelling process.

In any case, our aim is to offer an application which will be robust in sense of applicability on any city with appropriate input data, and which can be highly beneficial for urban and city-regional planners and environmental departments of the cities and to offer this app to a wide range of end-users in the future.

Question 4: What is the added value for scientists/urban stakeholders over existing services?

- Is there any commercial service available in the market that provides a similar solution? (i.e. which are the main "competitor services" offering alternative solutions to yours)? (Note: please list the "applications")
- What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to your service?
- Do you know any new service in progress of development (with TRL 7 or 8) that could compete in the future with your service?

For the competition, there are few well established similar commercial solutions and services, usually based on hydrological modelling and sure many new services in progress of development. For example, the OpenFlows FLOOD by BENTLEY^[1], Flood Modeller by Jacobs^[2], MIKE by DHI^[3] or services provided by Waterman Group^[4].

- Strengths of competitive solutions compared to our service:
 - o Well-known in the consultancy business
 - o Some of them allow for modelling in very high spatial detail
 - o Some of them are taking into consideration also the sub-surface runoff supported by sewage drainage in the cities etc.
- Strengths of our service:

- o Based on Copernicus data – allowing easy replication for any Copernicus city and also in the future, as Copernicus program guarantees harmonized data acquisition/production in following years
- o Running on DIAS – no demands on user own processing infrastructure

Based on satellite imageries – allowing to perform both historical analysis and rapid monitoring as a response on recent events

^[1] <https://www.bentley.com/en/products/product-line/hydraulics-and-hydrology-software/openflows-flood>

^[2] <https://www.floodmodeller.com>

^[3] <https://www.mikepoweredbydhi.com/products/mike-flood/integrated-flood-modelling>

^[4] <https://www.watermangroup.com/>

Question 5: How easily can your service be upscaled to other cities (both in Europe and outside Europe)?

It should be very straightforward to upscale this service to other cities. The only limitation is the availability of the local hydrology parameter.

Question 6: Is your service linked with existing Copernicus services?

Yes, C3S (precipitation data) and CLMS (Urban Atlas), Copernicus satellite data (Sentinels and VHR satellites)

Ap06 Urban Subsidence, Movements and Deformation Risk

Question 1: Describe your service-to-be in technical detail (include schemes if possible), while addressing the sub-questions.

The CURE Land Subsidence App aims to support cities with enriched information about land subsidence. To understand drivers and impacts of land subsidence at city level the intensity of terrain deformation hazard derived by means of MT InSAR technology needs to be integrated with additional supportive information. Analysis of spatial patterns of subsidence phenomena brings insights into hazard distribution and its magnitude. Especially important is identification of clusters of subsiding measurement points attributed to similar behavior and outlying points or clusters dissimilar to behavior of points in surroundings. Furthermore, given complex nature of potential drivers and size of observable objects in the urban environment multi-scale approach will be adopted. Distribution and chronology of urban evolution (expansion, densification) may affect both spatial and temporal patterns of land subsidence and should be assessed in relation to observed deformation rate. The module will consist of series of Python scripts responsible for spatial-temporal analytics and data fusion. Spatial associations will be analyzed within results from Copernicus European Ground Motion Service, EGMS (when it will be available), or from custom MT InSAR processing chain deployed on DIAS infrastructure. Next, the results will be integrated with temporal patterns derived from pan-European and global open datasets describing urban structure and height (Copernicus Urban Atlas with 3D component) and long-term built-up evolution (DLR's World Settlements Footprint-Evolution, JRC's GHSL). Output from module will be represented by standardized analytics providing added value derived from fusion of scalable inputs.

- **What data does your service need?**
 - Ground deformations (Copernicus EGMS / Results from custom interferometric analysis - based on Sentinel-1 or VHR – prepared by GISAT before the EGMS is available)
 - Land use (Copernicus Urban atlas / Custom land use map)
 - Built-up expansion (WSF-Evo / GHSL)
- **Does your code run with raw input data or does it require preprocessed data?**

The code does not run with raw Copernicus input data, the data need to be preprocessed.

- **How much storage does your interim and output data need? (Please provide two sizes, one for interim and one for output data)**
 - Interim: 1s-10s GB (excluding custom MT InSAR chain); 1s-10s TB (including custom MT InSAR chain)
 - Output: 10s-100s MB
- **Does your service contain more than one task (series of script executions)?**

MT InSAR chain will be run independently. The analytical service will be modular, but it shall be run as one series of Python scripts

- **What resources does your service need for processing one unit (Cores, RAM)?**

We cannot estimate this properly at this stage of the project. In general:

MT InSAR chain: The more cores the better. The more RAM the better.

Analytical chain 1 core, 16-32 GB RAM. Hours to days runtime.

- **Do you use Docker?**

we will use Docker

Question 2: Will your service be user-interactive (how?) or do you only provide output data/maps?

Very limited interactivity is expected as the service is extremely asynchronous. Simple user interface shall allow definition of basic variables.

- Definition of the AOI
- Selection of input components to be fused (from the list)
 - o Cop EGMS / custom MT InSAR outputs
 - o Built-up evolution
 - o Urban Atlas Land use map / Custom land use map

Specification of clustering options (variables)

Output maps shall be presented using proprietary web platform

Question 3: How do you see your service evolve on the long term (after the CURE project)?

We would like to continue running and offering the service after the CURE for more cities in Europe (primarily using Copernicus data: EGMS & Urban Atlas) or outside Europe (primarily using custom MT InSAR & land use data).

The service shall provide set of standardized derivative analytics related to spatial and temporal distribution of ground deformations based on fusion with Copernicus and global open datasets.

Question 4: What is the added value for scientists/urban stakeholders over existing services?

- Is there any commercial service available in the market that provides a similar solution? (i.e. which are the main "competitor services" offering alternative solutions to yours)? (Note: please list the "applications")
 - What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to your service?
 - Do you know any new service in progress of development (with TRL 7 or 8) that could compete in the future with your service?
1. We do not know of competing equivalent commercial service. Several European companies are providing MT InSAR services, e.g.: TRE-Altamira, e-Geos, SkyGeo, Sensar, Sarsense, Gamma RS, Planetek, NHazka, and several other start-up companies and institutions (BRGM, KIT, NGO, ...). EGMS online visualization platform will not provide comparable functionality.
 2. Most of the MT InSAR providers provide their own online platform for exploration of complex InSAR results with likely similar basic functionalities and specialized functions and visualizations depending on each service provider's expertise and business model.
 3. There might be other similar services in development. Gisat combines practical and scientific background in development of solutions based on MT InSAR technology, and proven record in deployment commercial online platform integrating and fusing MT InSAR results.

Question 5: How easily can your service be upscaled to other cities (both in Europe and outside Europe)?

It should be easy to upscale for cities in Europe where Urban Atlas land use map is available (after EGMS results from its first phase are operationally available in 2022). In the meantime, custom MT InSAR service need to be utilized to obtain comparable ground deformation data. Custom MT InSAR service might be generally utilized if customer needs input with different parameters, e.g. with higher spatial density of measurement points, custom period for deformation rate estimation, or using different deformation model.

Outside Europe ground deformation component relies on execution of custom MT InSAR service chain. Scaling depends on availability and nomenclature of custom land use map. If not available at all, the service may be downscaled to provide analytics only using global open datasets (WSF-Evol, GHSL).

Question 6: Is your service linked with existing Copernicus services?

Yes. Urban Atlas and also EGMS (when ready).

Ap07 Urban Air Quality

Question 1: Describe your service-to-be in technical detail (include schemes if possible), while addressing the sub-questions.

- What data does your service need?

Minimal data:

- CAMS: air quality reanalysis data
- CAMS: air pollutant emissions
- CLMS: Urban Atlas building height
- OpenStreetMaps: building locations and roadmap
- C3S: 2m temperature and 10m (vectorial) wind speed
- EIONET: Point Source emissions reported for LRTAP convention
- Does your code run with raw input data or does it require preprocessed data?

Preprocessed data (for all the datasets)

- How much storage does your interim and output data need? (Please provide two sizes, one for interim and one for output data)

For one city:

- Interim storage (temporary model output, which is later combined to annual mean concentration): 30 GB
- Final output: 200MB
- Does your service contain more than one task (series of script executions)?

Series of scripts: one Python preprocessing script per data input (point sources, traffic emissions, residential emissions, streetcanyon data, meteorology, background concentrations), scripts to start the model core (python wrapper around Fortran model core), scripts for postprocessing.

- **What resources does your service need for processing one unit (Cores, RAM)?**

Depends on the required runtime.

RAM: 16 GB

Number of cores: the more the better (the annual mean concentration is modelled day by day, but all days can run in parallel). Typically, we use 122 cores. Results are then available in 24 hours.

- **Do you use Docker?**

No.

Question 2: Will your service be user-interactive (how?) or do you only provide output data/maps?

Only output data. The model core is commercial software (partially owned by VITO, partially by Aarhus University). The AQ app is not scheduled to be implemented in the DIAS.

Question 3: How do you see your service evolve on the long term (after the CURE project)?

Continued updates based on model validations.

Question 4: What is the added value for scientists/urban stakeholders over existing services?

- **Is there any commercial service available in the market that provides a similar solution? (i.e. which are the main "competitor services" offering alternative solutions to yours)? (Note: please list the "applications")**
- **What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to your service?**
- **Do you know any new service in progress of development (with TRL 7 or 8) that could compete in the future with your service?**

We consider our service as a consultancy service, whereby high resolution urban pollutant concentration maps are provided as a service to regional / national / urban authorities, or to institutes providing pan-European data. Some more information on the these four type of clients:

- Many European national / regional or urban authorities (e.g. the UK, France, Belgium, the Netherlands, Germany, Sweden, Finland) have many year's expertise in producing air quality maps using AQ models for their region and cities. More recently, at high resolution as we propose here. These models are often tailored to use the local datasets (e.g. traffic data, fleet composition), and therefore provide a much better quality than the CURE AQ application. In some cases the authorities run the models themselves, in other regions the work is often subcontracted out (as frameworks or contracts) to local experts: at universities, research institutes or consultancies. Bottomline: they prefer to use their own local datasets.
- The next group of stakeholders are cities / regions / countries who do not use a high-resolution AQ model but do have a lot of detailed information (traffic flows, fleet data, information on residential sources). For these stakeholders, the quality of an AQ application based on the local data will always outperform the AQ model solely based on Copernicus data. Thus again, they prefer to use their own local datasets.
- A third group of stakeholders are those cities / regions / countries lacking sufficient local datasets and resources (economically and technically) to prepare urban scale maps, to which we aim this CURE service.
- A final group of potential clients considers the institutes willing to provide a pan-European service. At these moment, there are no services that model the air quality at street-level scale throughout Europe. There are however services relying on modelling at a lower resolution, and services that rely on air quality measurements. Both types of services however often fail to incorporate the street canyon contributions^[1], which are important for the population exposure. A pan-European high-resolution (street-level) modelling service would moreover provide the ideal tool to compare cities with each other.

Competitors:

- There are some competitors that offer a similar service. An example is ADMS Urban software (TRL9) (<http://www.cerc.co.uk/environmental-software/ADMS-Urban-model.html#:~:text=What%20is%20ADMS%20Urban%3F,urban%20areas%2C%20cities%20and%20towns.&text=investigation%20of%20air%20quality%20management,air%20pollution%20exposure%20studies>), which provide a similar consultancy service. We have somewhat more experience with Copernicus data as driver for the models (important for a pan-European service), and we have more connections with the market in Eastern EU (important for services for urban, regional and national authorities in that region).
- Many open source air quality models exist (e.g. AERMOD). These models could be used in combination with the CAMS data by local authorities or research institutes. It however requires a lot of experience with big data and (linux) programming to get these models up and running, leading to high costs.

For detailed information and competitors and the market situation: see reports of the EU H2020 AirQast project.

[\[1\]](#) For the low-resolution modelling chains, street-canyons or not considered in the chain. Services based on measurements, on the other hand, are strongly influenced by the location of the measurement stations. As many cities lack stations in street canyons (e.g. Sofia), these services will also miss the peak values.

Question 5: How easily can your service be upscaled to other cities (both in Europe and outside Europe)?

Current service can easily be deployed for all EU cities (although some assumptions will have to be made for buildings height for non-capitals, as the building height layer of CLMS is only available for the capitals).

Deployment outside Europe requires a lot of changes, as many of the currently used datasets are only available EU-wide (emissions, background concentrations). Often global alternatives exist (e.g. CAMS global emissions and reanalysis), but the quality of these product is often lower.

Question 6: Is your service linked with existing Copernicus services?

CAMS, C3S, CLMS => see data

Ap08 Urban Thermal Comfort

Question 1: Describe your service-to-be in technical detail (include schemes if possible), while addressing the sub-questions.

The CURE Thermal Comfort App is based on the urban climate model UrbClim, developed by VITO, for which recently a high resolution thermal comfort module is developed (Lauwaet et al., 2020^[1]). This module calculates hourly Wet Bulb Globe Temperature values for a selected typical hot day in summer (Netcdf file), which are translated in postprocessing to heat stress maps, based on international or local threshold values (Geotiff file). The module consists of a series of Python scripts. As input data, local meteorological variables (air temperature, humidity, wind speed, radiation and land surface temperature) are needed that are provided by the 100m resolution UrbClim model. Furthermore, a very high resolution land use map is needed, which is combined with building height and tree height information in a preprocessing step.

^[1] Lauwaet D., Maiheu B., De Ridder K., Boëne W., Hooyberghs H., Demuzere M., Verdonck M.-L., 2020. A New Method to Assess Fine-Scale Outdoor Thermal Comfort for Urban Agglomerations. *Climate*, 8, 6; doi:10.3390/cli8010006.

- What data does your service need?

The service needs 2 input files: a Netcdf file containing the 100m resolution UrbClim meteorological variables, and a Geotiff file with the very high resolution land use map.

- **Does your code run with raw input data or does it require preprocessed data?**

The code does not run with raw Copernicus input data, the data need to be preprocessed.

- **How much storage does your interim and output data need? (Please provide two sizes, one for interim and one for output data)**

For each city:

As interim data, the code produces a few Geotiff files and a Netcdf file. The size depends largely on the chosen domain size, but is typically in the order of a few Gb.

As output data the code produces one or more Geotiff files with a typical size in the order of a few hundred Mb.

- **Does your service contain more than one task (series of script executions)?**

No, it consists of one series of Python scripts.

- **What resources does your service need for processing one unit (Cores, RAM)?**

The code runs on a single core with 16 (or more) Gb RAM and runs for a few hours to a day (depending on the domain size).

- **Do you use Docker?**

Yes, we have expertise with Docker. VITO's IT team uses Docker regularly to run our models in a client's environment.

Question 2: Will your service be user-interactive (how?) or do you only provide output data/maps?

Ideally, we have a user-interactive service in mind, where the user can alter (or upload) the input very high resolution land use map. This would allow the user to assess their own urban adaptation scenarios.

This aspect of the service can perhaps be discussed/developed in collaboration with GISAT, who have experience with user-interactive map services.

Question 3: How do you see your service evolve on the long term (after the CURE project)?

We aim to continue this work after the CURE project and integrate the service in the Copernicus framework. As VITO has already delivered 100m resolution urban climate data for 100 European cities to Copernicus, our service can be used in each of these cities to make high

resolution thermal comfort maps. The service could also be linked to CMIP5 (or CMIP6) climate change data, to assess whether green-blue urban adaptation measures are effective in reducing the heat stress impact of climate change.

Question 4: What is the added value for scientists/urban stakeholders over existing services?

- Is there any commercial service available in the market that provides a similar solution? (i.e. which are the main "competitor services" offering alternative solutions to yours)? (Note: please list the "applications")
- What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to your service?
- Do you know any new service in progress of development (with TRL 7 or 8) that could compete in the future with your service?

There are a few commercial software packages (e.g. ENVI-met[1] and FLUENT[2]) that can deliver similar high resolution thermal comfort maps for buildings/city quarters and that are used by consultancy firms/research institutes in projects for urban authorities.

Strengths compared to our service:

- Well-known in the consultancy business
- Allow for a lot of detail in the input data (lots of scenario options)

Weaknesses compared to our service:

- Expensive to set up and run
- Not possible to model large areas
- Make use of idealized settings, difficult to validate against measurements

Some consultancy companies/research institutes make use of high resolution remote sensing imagery, combined with empirical relations or measurements, to estimate spatial heat stress patterns in cities (e.g. Koopmans et al., 2020[3]).

Strengths compared to our service:

- Low-cost methodology
- Can be applied for very large areas

Weaknesses compared to our service:

- Not possible to do scenario analyses
- Difficult to validate against measurements

Most probably there are other services in development since this is a growing market, but none of these have the direct links to Copernicus and scientific background that our service has.

[1] <https://www.envi-met.com/buy-now/>

[2] <https://www.ansys.com/products/fluids/ansys-fluent>

[3] <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360132320303644>

Question 5: How easily can your service be upscaled to other cities (both in Europe and outside Europe)?

It should be very straightforward to upscale this service to the 100 European cities that have been modelled with the UrbClim model in the past, and for which the data are available in the Copernicus Data Store. The only limitation is the availability of the VHR land use map, but we assume these are/will become available soon for a large number of cities, or can be made for a limited cost.

For other cities (both inside and outside Europe) we first need to perform 100m resolution UrbClim simulations, which comes with an additional cost.

In principle this service can relatively easy operate on a global scale

Question 6: Is your service linked with existing Copernicus services?

Yes, C3S and CLMS => see scheme above

Ap09 Urban Heat Storage Monitoring

Question 1: Describe your service-to-be in technical detail (include schemes if possible), while addressing the sub-questions.

The CURE Urban Heat Storage Monitoring App to be developed by FORTH and UNIBAS, is aiming at delivering heat storage estimations over cities. Urban Heat Storage () is the net flow of heat stored in urban canopy and represents all the mechanisms of storage of energy within the volume, i.e., the air, on trees, in buildings constructed in the ground, etc. Observations of global temperature evolution indicate a pronounced air temperature warming, since an increase in the occurrence of heat waves and the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effects tends to exacerbate such warming. Among all the effects caused by the substitution of natural ecosystems for urban land-use, the most pronounced is the increase in the amount of energy stored in the urban canopy (especially in buildings), which is approximately 2-6 times larger than in non-urban canopies. The slow release of this energy, stored mainly in the buildings and paved surfaces of cities, causes the UHI effect and it is therefore related to the energy efficiency and consumption in cities. In this framework, the CURE application will deploy various EO and in-situ urban data, such as land cover, geometry, radiation and air/surface temperature, towards monitoring urban heat storage.

The urban heat storage retrieval will be based on the Objective Hysteresis Model (Offerle et al. 2005^[1]).

[1] Offerle, B., Grimmond, C.S.B.B., Fortuniak, K., 2005. Heat storage and anthropogenic heat flux in relation to the energy balance of a central European city centre. *Int. J. Climatol.* 25, 1405–1419. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.1198>

- **What data does your service need?**
 - Dynamim surface temperature (from AP01)
 - Dynamic Surface Cover Fractions in 100 m spatial resolution
 - 3D information on the buildings and trees height
 - Net-all wave radiation flux
 - Time rate of change for net all-wave radiation at the surface
 - Coefficients associated to response of the surface cover due the energy input (i.e. thermal properties of the urban materials in the city).

- **Does your code run with raw input data or does it require preprocessed data?**

The method does not run with raw Copernicus input data, the data need to be preprocessed.

- **How much storage does your interim and output data need? (Please provide two sizes, one for interim and one for output data)**

For each city:

The method will not probably not produce any interim data.

As output data the method will produce a Geotiff files with a typical size in the order of a few hundred Mb.

- **Does your service contain more than one task (series of script executions)?**

There is no service available at the moment. The scripting is under development, but we aim to build it into a single script with several functions.

- **What resources does your service need for processing one unit (Cores, RAM)?**

NA

- **Do you use Docker?**

No, we will use Docker for the first time in CURE.

Question 2: Will your service be user-interactive (how?) or do you only provide output data/maps?

It is highly unlikely that this application could be made user-interactive.

Question 3: How do you see your service evolve on the long term (after the CURE project)?

We aim to continue this work after the CURE project, but lots of work would necessary before this can be a service integrated in the Copernicus framework.

Question 4: What is the added value for scientists/urban stakeholders over existing services?

- **Is there any commercial service available in the market that provides a similar solution? (i.e. which are the main "competitor services" offering alternative solutions to yours)? (Note: please list the "applications")**
- **What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to your service?**
- **Do you know any new service in progress of development (with TRL 7 or 8) that could compete in the future with your service?**

There are no similar services available for delivering urban heat storage maps from satellite and other EO data. All efforts are at the moment on a research level and the CURE app will be the first to allow insights on the method transformation into a service.

Question 5: How easily can your service be upscaled to other cities (both in Europe and outside Europe)?

Very difficult. It would require data collection, manual interpretation and a lot of scientific experimenting, for transferring the method to other cities.

Question 6: Is your service linked with existing Copernicus services?

Yes, C3S and CLMS since it uses input data from AP01.

Ap10 Nature-based Solutions

Question 1: Describe your service-to-be in technical detail (include schemes if possible), while addressing the sub-questions.

- **What data does your service need?**

The NBS App will compare 3 different scenarios based on different resolution inputs: LiDAR, Euro Maps 3D, DSM generated by DLR (tri- stereo imagery), NDVI, imperviousness, albedo and cadaster information (year of construction and protection level). The NBS App sets its basis on the methodology proposed in Decumanus, which identifies potential green roofs from slope computation and identification of % flat surface. It also combines NDVI to detect surfaces already vegetated. The definition of flat or quasi-flat roofs will be adjusted on a case by case basis, according to local policies. Prioritization of potential green roof will be then calculated by discarding protected buildings where such interventions are not feasible due to legal restrictions, again considering a case by case approach. A threshold for load capacity based on the year of construction will determine which buildings are more suitable to host green roofs without major interventions on the structure. Albedo calculation and imperviousness will also be considered as factors to determine the prioritized buildings. It is based on a series of Python scripts. GIS3D Viewer will be used as a model for the urban area and will therefore permit to address some other geometric parameters and shading effects. The idea is that some functions will be interactive, and the users will have the possibility to select all parameters or choose only some of them.

The nature of the application makes it suitable for “static assessment”. Potential and prioritization of green roofs is evaluated once, in a precise time period and do not require short term evolution assessment of parameters.

- **Does your code run with raw input data or does it require preprocessed data?**

Preprocessed data

- **How much storage does your interim and output data need? (Please provide two sizes, one for interim and one for output data)**

Output should be around few hundreds of Megabytes, while interim would be much heavier (in the order of some tens of Gigabytes).

- **Does your service contain more than one task (series of script executions)?**

Yes, it contains a series of scripts that run lineally

- **What resources does your service need for processing one unit (Cores, RAM)?**

At present we cannot say much for the number of cores. For the RAM, 8GB of RAM might be suitable.

- **Do you use Docker?**

No

Question 2: Will your service be user-interactive (how?) or do you only provide output data/maps?

Main output is a map but in the final phase of the process may include user interactive component (GIS3D Viewer for interactive visualization)

Question 3: How do you see your service evolve on the long term (after the CURE project)?

Evolution in the long-term may include an inventory of solutions to help choosing the appropriate type of green roof or complementary solutions according to effectiveness parameters and building constructive typology.

Question 4: What is the added value for scientists/urban stakeholders over existing services?

- **Is there any commercial service available in the market that provides a similar solution? (i.e. which are the main "competitor services" offering alternative solutions to yours)? (Note: please list the "applications")**

Green City is an online tool developed by TerraNIS for the study, monitoring and management of urban vegetation and green areas in cities and to accompany them in their ecological transition. It provides a diagnosis of the vegetation, quantifies it and qualifies it considering biodiversity and well-being aspects.

For that the tool uses satellite images of different resolutions (Pléiades and Sentinel-2 images), open data (Open street map and other sources) and INSEE data (French National Institute for Statistics and Economic Studies). The processing of this data allows the calculation of different simple and synthetic indicators that can be displayed in a dashboard. It also allows to guide decisions and select priority areas of action, by introducing target values for each indicator.

Despite not being a tool focused on green roofs, in their diagnosis green roofs could also be included. Besides this, the tool includes the possibility to prioritize intervention

areas thanks to the possibility of introducing target values for the indicators, that is something that could be included in our development.

- **What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to your service?**

Our tool is more specific, and it is focused on the greening potential of roofs, excluding those that could not be transformed into green roofs for different reasons (slope, load limits, etc.).

City Green is focused in the diagnosis of the green areas of the city (that could also include green roofs, but not sure about this), but does not calculate its greening potential. Introducing target values the user can identify the areas that don't reach the values in order to prioritize the interventions, but this does not mean that reaching the objective will be feasible.

The service is only available for Toulouse it is necessary to contact them to include new cities

- **Do you know any new service in progress of development (with TRL 7 or 8) that could compete in the future with your service?**

A paper of 2016 on estimating potential green cover at rooftop level using 3D data obtained by LiDAR was analyzed, but seems that funds were linked to national and post-doctoral grant and no advances have been found on the method used. Santos T et al. (2016). *Quantifying the City's Green Area Potential Gain Using Remote Sensing Data. Sustainability 2016, 8(12), 1247; <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8121247>*

Question 5: How easily can your service be upscaled to other cities (both in Europe and outside Europe)?

It depends on the availability of inputs data

Question 6: Is your service linked with existing Copernicus services?

Yes, mainly CLSM, but can be associated to C3S and thermal comfort application (to be further discussed).

Ap11 Health Impacts

Question 1: Describe your service-to-be in technical detail (include schemes if possible), while addressing the sub-questions.

Application 11 Health impacts and health costs of air pollution will build on the existing EVA model developed by Aarhus University. The integrated model system is based on the impact-pathway chain and is used for assessment of health impacts from air pollution, including both health effects and related external costs (sometimes also referred to as “indirect costs”) which can be attributed to air pollution exposure. Chemical components important for health impacts and included in the EVA system are: nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulphur dioxide (SO₂), ozone (O₃) and particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), where the individual constituents of PM_{2.5} are: mineral dust, black carbon (BC), organic matter (OM), secondary inorganic aerosols (SIA – i.e. nitrate, sulphate and ammonia), secondary organic aerosols (SOA) and sea salt.

The EVA model is coupled to the air pollution models DEHM (Danish Eulerian Hemispheric Model) and UBM (Urban Background Model) for regional-scale and local-scale health impact assessments, respectively. EVA includes gridded population data, exposure-response functions for health impacts in terms of morbidity and mortality, and economic valuation of the health impacts from air pollution.

The EVA system includes the best available and most accurate, yet computationally demanding methods, used in each part of the impact-pathway chain. The EVA system uses comprehensive and thoroughly tested chemistry-transport models when calculating air pollution levels in general as well as scenarios describing how specific changes in emissions of pollutants to the air affect air pollution levels at regional and local scale.

To calculate the impacts of the total air pollution levels or of emissions from a specific source or sector, concentrations and address-level population data are combined to estimate human exposure, and then the response is calculated using an exposure-response function (ERF) of the following form: $R = A \cdot C \cdot P$, where R is the response (e.g. in cases, days, or episodes), C the concentration (i.e. the total concentration or additional concentration resulting from emissions of a particular emission source), P the affected share of the population, and A is an empirically determined constant for the particular health outcome, typically obtained from published cohort studies.

We are not sure yet how the model runs in more technical detail than this, as it is patented and copyrighted by Aarhus University and will only be made available to CWare/CURE as an output analyses. However the service will be city specific in the beginning, before we can hopefully upscale the service to include more cities. However, if the air quality data is in the same format and year, for example for Berlin and Sofia, the model would be able to run both

cities at once and provide output data for both Berlin and Sofia. But the analyses of the results would require a bit more time when two cities are included, compared to just one city.

- What data does your service need?

Air quality data from Sofia

- Does your code run with raw input data or does it require preprocessed data?

Processed data, format to be agreed with VITO

- How much storage does your interim and output data need? (Please provide two sizes, one for interim and one for output data)

tbd

- Does your service contain more than one task (series of script executions)?

tbd

- What resources does your service need for processing one unit (Cores, RAM)?

tbd

- Do you use Docker?

No

Question 2: Will your service be user-interactive (how?) or do you only provide output data/maps?

It will for sure include output as data/a thorough analyses of Sofia and Copenhagen.

Question 3: How do you see your service evolve on the long term (after the CURE project)?

We envision an application that bundles the air quality data with health data for a city, to be used as a decision tool for local governments, city planners etc. The application will need air pollution data from each city and can from there run the model to show health costs. The application should be made interactive and should have the ability for the user to tweak the different parameters such that e.g. the effect would be seen if all cars in the city went electric etc. and what that would mean in terms of monetary values of hospitalisations, mortality etc. and how diseases (cardiovascular and respiratory) are affected by different levels of air pollution. In the long term, once the research link between cause and effect becomes better known, the application should also include e.g. mental health, autism and diabetes. As well as the effects of air pollution on children aged 0-5, this is an important developmental stage in each person's life, and air pollution can have the ability to greatly negatively influence the brain and other bodily functions.

Question 4: What is the added value for scientists/urban stakeholders over existing services?

- **Is there any commercial service available in the market that provides a similar solution? (i.e. which are the main "competitor services" offering alternative solutions to yours)? (Note: please list the "applications")**
- **What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to your service?**
- **Do you know any new service in progress of development (with TRL 7 or 8) that could compete in the future with your service?**

Denmark is in the unique position of having a central register with information regarding address, sex and age for all persons in the country. The CPR dataset (Central Personedata Register) is set into coordinates by matching the dataset with the national register of addresses, and making it into 1 km x 1km grid cells.

The EVA system describes the health effects of:

- Bronchitis in adults
- Bronchitis and asthma in children
- Sick days
- Hospital admissions for respiratory and cardiovascular diseases
- Lung cancer
- Acute deaths (caused by short term exposure)
- Years of Life Lost (caused by longterm exposure)
- Total amount of deaths (=chronic years lost/10,6* + acute deaths)

And includes NO₂, CO₂, PM_{2,5} and PM₁₀, SO₂ and O₃.

There are two other known Air Pollution Health Risk Assessment Tools on a regional level, Aphekom and EcoSense. We refer to below tables for comparison of the three systems (Anenberg, S. C., Belova, A., Brandt, J., Fann, N., Greco, S., Guttikunda, S., ... Van Dingenen, R. (2016). Survey of Ambient Air Pollution Health Risk Assessment Tools. Risk Analysis, 36(9), 1718–1736. doi:10.1111/risa.12540).

Table IV. Key Technical Characteristics of Tools with Regional (i.e., Multiple Countries in One World Region) Scope

Characteristic	Aphekom	EVA	EcoSense
Region:	Europe	Northern Hemisphere	Europe
National		x	x
City-level	x	x	x
Grid		x	x
Pollutants:			
PM _{2.5}	x	x	x
PM ₁₀	x	x	x
Ozone	x	x	x
NO ₂		x	x
SO ₂		x	x
CO		x	
Other		Dioxins, mercury, black carbon	Heavy metals, dioxins, radio nuclides
Health outcome:			
Mortality (cases)	x	x	x
Disability-adjusted life years (DALY) or years of life lost (YLL)	x	x	x
Morbidity (cases)	x	x	x

Table V. PM_{2.5} Concentration-Response, Population, and Baseline Incidence Data Sources for Tools with Regional Scope

Characteristic	Aphekom	EVA	EcoSense
PM_{2.5} concentration-response relationship:			
User-defined		x	
American Cancer Society ⁽⁵⁶⁾	x	x	
Other	Several others ⁽⁵⁷⁻⁵⁹⁾	WHO	WHO ⁽⁴⁷⁾
Population data source:			
User-defined	x	x	
Other		GEOSTAT	JRC population density grid ⁽⁶⁰⁾ with enhancements
Baseline incidence data source:			
User-defined	x		
World Health Organization		x	
Other			EUROSTAT, national statistics

Table VI. Key Operational Characteristics of Tools with Regional Scope

Characteristic	Aphekom	EVA	EcoSense
Format:			
Software download		x	
Microsoft office program	x		
Web based			x
Open source	x		
Proprietary		x	x
Peer reviewed/policy applications:			
Peer reviewed	x	x	x
Used for policy applications	x	x	x

Other approaches:

Demographic data and life expectancy can be taken from Eurostat (population by age and sex, and life expectancy by age and sex), and the mortality data can be taken from WHO (European detailed mortality database). The exposure-response relationship and the population at risk can be selected by following a recommendation from the Health Risks of Air Pollution in Europe (HRAPIE project - WHO, Health risks of air pollution in Europe – HRAPIE project: New emerging risks to health from air pollution — Results from the survey of experts , World Health Organization). Quantifications of health impacts are done individually for these air pollutants, and they cannot be added together, as they exhibit some degree of correlation, positive or negative. For example, when adding together the values for PM and NO, this may lead to double counting of the effects of NO up to 30 %. These quantifications can then be directly converted to population exposure and premature deaths or years of life lost, but this does not provide a quantification of the health and economic impact (http://www.euro.who.int/data/assets/pdf_file/0006/238956/Health_risks_air_pollution_HRAPIE_project.pdf?ua=1)

There is also a recent study funded by Public Health England (PHE) which has used a microsimulation model to produce longitudinal projections for the UK, but is not city specific and only looks at PM_{2.5} and NO₂, hence lacking other crucial pollutants. This study used a dynamic microsimulation model to predict the future health and economic impact of the air pollutants PM_{2.5} and NO₂ to the year 2035. This microsimulation examined data on air pollution exposure by age and sex, making use of disease and population data collected from the literature and from publicly available databases. The microsimulation method is an advanced method for modelling chronic diseases because of its capacity to simulate entire populations at an individual level over a lifetime.

The microsimulation model can be expanded to include additional pollutants and different populations but further work would be needed to develop the model. (<https://journals.plos.org/plosmedicine/article?id=10.1371/journal.pmed.1002602>)

Question 5: How easily can your service be upscaled to other cities (both in Europe and outside Europe)?

The EVA model can run on “default settings” for all cities in Europe, so in principle the upscaling could be fairly easily done. However, if a more detailed analyses is desired, local data is needed, such as the air quality data and the analyses can also be tailored better if there are local data sources on the inhabitants of the city (number of inhabitants + age + sex + living location).

Question 6: Is your service linked with existing Copernicus services?

Yes and No. Aarhus University and the EVA model is right now part of two Copernicus service projects, one of them is the CAMS52, however the model does not build on the existing Copernicus services but rather applies the model to these services as a prognosis for air quality.